

NMR spectra:

Cp2MoH2_1HNMR_C6D6.csv :	[Cp ₂ MoH ₂] ¹ H NMR in C ₆ D ₆
Cp2WH2_1HNMR_C6D6.csv :	[Cp ₂ WH ₂] ¹ H NMR in C ₆ D ₆
1a_1HNMR_CDCl3.csv :	[Cp ₂ MoCl ₂] ¹ H NMR in CDCl ₃
1a_13CNMR_CDCl3.csv:	[Cp ₂ MoCl ₂] ¹³ C NMR in CDCl ₃
1a_1HNMR_D2O.csv :	[Cp ₂ MoCl ₂] ¹ H NMR in D ₂ O
1b_1HNMR_CD3OD.csv :	[Cp ₂ Mo(μ-OH) ₂ MoCp ₂](pTsO) ₂ ¹ H NMR in MeOD
1b_13CNMR_CD3OD.csv:	[Cp ₂ Mo(μ-OH) ₂ MoCp ₂](pTsO) ₂ ¹³ C NMR in MeOD
1b_1HNMR_D2O.csv :	[Cp ₂ Mo(μ-OH) ₂ MoCp ₂](pTsO) ₂ in D ₂ O
2a_1HNMR_CDCl3.csv :	[Cp ₂ WCl ₂] ¹ H NMR in CDCl ₃
2a_13CNMR_CDCl3.csv:	[Cp ₂ WCl ₂] ¹³ C NMR in CDCl ₃
2a_1HNMR_D2O.csv :	[Cp ₂ WCl ₂] ¹ H NMR in D ₂ O
2b_1HNMR_CD3OD.csv :	[Cp ₂ W(μ-OH) ₂ WCp ₂](pTsO) ₂ ¹ H NMR in MeOD
2b_13CNMR_CD3OD.csv:	[Cp ₂ W(μ-OH) ₂ WCp ₂](pTsO) ₂ ¹³ C NMR in MeOD
2b_1HNMR_D2O.csv :	[Cp ₂ W(μ-OH) ₂ WCp ₂](pTsO) ₂ in D ₂ O
3_1HNMR_DMF_1h.csv :	[Cp ₂ Mo(pTsO) ₂] ¹ H NMR in DMF-d ₇ after 1 hour
3_1HNMR_DMF_6days.csv :	[Cp ₂ Mo(pTsO) ₂] ¹ H NMR in DMF-d ₇ after 6 days
3_13CNMR_DMF.csv :	[Cp ₂ Mo(pTsO) ₂] ¹³ C NMR in DMF-d ₇
3_1HNMR_D2O.csv :	[Cp ₂ Mo(pTsO) ₂] ¹ H NMR in D ₂ O
4_1HNMR_DMF_1h.csv :	[Cp ₂ W(pTsO) ₂] ¹ H NMR in DMF-d ₇ after 1 hour
4_1HNMR_DMF_6days.csv :	[Cp ₂ W(pTsO) ₂] ¹ H NMR in DMF-d ₇ after 6 days
4_13CNMR_DMF.csv :	[Cp ₂ W(pTsO) ₂] ¹³ C NMR in DMF-d ₇
4_1HNMR_D2O.csv :	[Cp ₂ W(pTsO) ₂] ¹ H NMR in D ₂ O

Titration Data:

1a_Titration_1-4.csv :	4 Titration curves of [Cp ₂ MoCl ₂] with relevant data.
1b_Titration_1-4.csv :	4 Titration curves of [Cp ₂ Mo(μ-OH) ₂ MoCp ₂](pTsO) ₂ with relevant data.
2a_Titration_1-4.csv :	4 Titration curves of [Cp ₂ WCl ₂] with relevant data.
2b_Titration_1-4.csv :	4 Titration curves of [Cp ₂ W(μ-OH) ₂ WCp ₂](pTsO) ₂ with relevant data.
1a_Titration_reverse.csv :	Titration curve of [Cp ₂ MoCl ₂] from basic pH with relevant data.
1b_Titration_reverse.csv :	Titration curve of [Cp ₂ Mo(μ-OH) ₂ MoCp ₂](pTsO) ₂ from basic pH with relevant data.